

My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem: A Workshop on how to Promote an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem

Dag Balkmar, Anne-Charlott Callerstig, Gry Agnete Alsos, Tina Bedenik, Marit Breivik-Meyer, Sibylle Heilbrunn, Marta Lindvert, Elisabet Ljunggren, Maura McAdam, and Caren Weinberg

Tool 3

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Levelling the field: A three-part toolbox

This publication is part of a three-part toolbox:

1. *Levelling the field: A Guide to an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem* provides a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship from an ecosystem perspective.
2. *The Gendered Nature of Tech Entrepreneurship: Understanding the Gender-Divide in Tech Entrepreneurship* is about “the what and whys” related to gender and entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on tech entrepreneurship.
3. *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem: A Workshop on How to Promote an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem* provides a format to enhance knowledge, ability and collaboration in an ecosystem focusing on *norm-reflexive ability for change* among actors in the ecosystem.

These three tools are meant as complementary components to inspire change. With the guidebook providing a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship, the report provides deeper *insights into different aspects of gender and inclusion*, and the workshop provides a *format and methods* to enhance knowledge, ability, and collaboration in the ecosystem.

Index

WOMEN IN TECH ENTREPRENEURSHIP: THE HARD TRUTHS OF AN UPHILL BATTLE?	5
- THE AIM OF THE WORKSHOP	6
- METHODOLOGY	7
THE ROLE OF NORM-REFLEXIVITY AND HOW TO PROMOTE IT	8
- PERSONAS	8
- BETTER STORIES	9
- WORKSHOP OUTLINE	10
DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE WORKSHOP SESSIONS	11
REFERENCES	18
APPENDIX	19

Women in tech entrepreneurship: The hard truths of an uphill battle?

Most regional entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem frameworks have the aspiration that entrepreneurs should have equal access to resources, participation, and support, as well as an equal chance of a successful outcome. Yet, in most parts of the world, women and minority groups remain underrepresented in entrepreneurial technological ecosystems. Gender is a decisive factor in all parts of the ecosystem. Women are underrepresented in relevant education, they report difficulties when pursuing a career in tech companies and receive less pay, they are underrepresented among start-ups and only a small portion of the investment capital goes to female entrepreneurs.

These bleak facts are further underlined by the many reports showing how diversity and inclusion is a key factor for achieving successful companies, meeting the diverse needs of customer groups, and enabling inclusive innovation outcomes.

The good news is that the situation can change! This publication contains the basic principles and advice for how to organize a co-creative workshop between actors in an ecosystem to jointly develop actions for change and promote learning.

Who is this instruction for?

This instruction is intended for the main facilitator and organizer of the workshop. How to make ecosystems more inclusive has been addressed in a three-part toolbox to inspire change:

1. *Levelling the field: Guide to an Inclusive Entrepreneurial Ecosystem* provides a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship from an ecosystem perspective.
2. *The Gendered Nature of Tech Entrepreneurship: Understanding the Gender-divide in Tech Entrepreneurship* is about “the what and whys” related to gender and entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on technical entrepreneurship.
3. *My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem: A Workshop on How to Promote an Inclusive Entrepreneurship Ecosystem* provides a format to enhance knowledge, ability and collaboration in an ecosystem focusing on *norm-reflexive ability for change* among actors in the ecosystem.

With the guidebook providing a basic understanding of *how to promote* inclusive entrepreneurship, the report provides *insights*, and the workshop provides a *format* to enhance knowledge, ability, and collaboration in the ecosystem. These tools build on the findings of the GENRE project: *Overcoming the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Gender Divide: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*.¹

The aim of the workshop

The main aim of the workshop is threefold; to spur collaboration and exchange among ecosystem actors; to enhance knowledge and learning, and finally; to co-create solutions to inspire change in individual actors as well as joint efforts to promote an inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem.

The overall questions addressed in the workshop can be summarized in two simple, yet difficult questions: What is the problem in our entrepreneurial ecosystem? Why and how can we fix it? These questions are addressed in a systematic way through different steps that will enable the participants to better understand the problems faced by women entrepreneurs and other groups facing different forms of inequalities. Participants will be given examples of approaches to the identified problems as well as initiatives created by real actors in real

¹ GENRE focuses on the cultural embeddedness and interactions of gender, technology, entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystems by providing a comparison between the four participating countries: Ireland, Sweden, Norway and Israel. In the GENRE project, we have conducted interviews with female and male entrepreneurs, with incubator managers and financiers, in Ireland, Sweden, Norway, and Israel. In doing so, we build knowledge on how contextual factors are constitutive of the strategies which women technology entrepreneurs adopt to develop, grow and enhance their businesses. The project focuses on a specific facet of gender in entrepreneurship: namely women’s technology entrepreneurship but the guidebook can be utilized in different contexts as well.

ecosystems. The participants will get inspiration but will also be encouraged to critically reflect upon opportunities and challenges to co-create ideas for better stories and actions to develop their own practices and suggest ways to collaborate in the future.

The workshop results in four main deliverables:

1. Collaboration

The output from the workshop is that actors in the various parts of the ecosystem will get to know each other, exchange inspiring initiatives that are already in place and to initiate ways to collaborate in the future.

2. Knowledge building

The workshop will result in increased knowledge on how equality can be understood from an ecosystem perspective and increased ability to critically reflect upon and design equality initiatives for ecosystem actors.

3. Co-creation

Part of the output from the workshop consists of ideas developed by participants for concrete actions individually and jointly; input for policy recommendations and a better understanding of questions that still need to be answered (missing insights or knowledge).

4. My ecosystem, the better story

After the workshop a publication will be made and distributed that summarizes important findings from the workshop, inspiring practice and recommendations made.

Methodology

The workshop has been inspired by the methodology of critical design and the Open studio methodology and the way it has been practiced in gender action-oriented research projects.² In short, the Open studio methodology has been designed to facilitate collaborative initiatives to design policy solutions for complex societal challenges bringing together multiple expertise, including the user experience.³

The workshop aims to enhance knowledge, ability and collaboration in an ecosystem focusing on *norm-reflexive ability for change* among actors in the ecosystem. Two concepts - *personas* and *better stories* - are used in the workshop as learning tools, explained below.

² Kerremans et al., 2021

³ Boyer, Cook and Steinberg, 2011

The role of norm-reflexivity and how to promote it

One of the underlying problems identified as to why there are so few women in technical entrepreneurship is implicit norms about who is viewed as the ideal entrepreneurs. Such norms influence our understanding of how entrepreneurs should behave, look and what they should work with. The classic example is highly masculinized ideals of behavior reflected in the iconification of tech entrepreneurs such as Elon Musk or Bill Gates whereas persons, or ideas, that do not fit into this norm may have been seen as having less potential. A study from Sweden showed that women and men with the same backgrounds were judged differently by a group of investors, which led to different funding outcomes.⁴ The investors, a group of both women and men, were not aware of how they assessed persons differently based on underlying assumptions of women and men.

A possible solution to this problem is to strengthen ecosystem actors' ability to detect and reflect upon norms. Norm-reflexivity can be promoted in many ways, one being to train actors to detect and reflect upon present norms, and how some norms may privilege certain groups and perspectives over others. This will also make it easier to detect and reflect on potential entrepreneurial possibilities among non-conformers or deviants of the norms.

Personas

We have developed several *personas* to spur reflections and discussions with regards to norms and unconscious bias related to entrepreneurship (see appendix below). Personas are archetypes of tech entrepreneurs designed to address specific problems that the persona faces.

⁴ Malmström & Johansson, 2015

We have developed two types of personas 1) archetypical *norm personas* (e.g., the “typical” representation of a tech entrepreneur) and 2) *alternative personas*, representing minority or non-typical entrepreneurs. Alternative personas, which represent different entrepreneur categories than those more common and mainstream, can be helpful to better engage in more diverse experiences and develop strategies that better fit a wider range of entrepreneurs lifeworld’s.⁵ Alternative personas can also uncover taken-for-granted assumptions which constrain the possibilities for promoting more inclusive ecosystems.

There are several norm personas and alternative personas to choose from for the workshop.⁶ The idea is that these personas represent different positions in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. In the workshop, the personas will be used to reflect upon the situation for different groups, the more privileged position of the norm-personas and the problems and solutions that can be developed for those who are in minority or not the “typical” entrepreneurs. Discussions should depart from questions such as the following:

For the norm persona

- What specific attributes does this person have that can give the person privileges as an entrepreneur that non-normative persons or groups lack?
- In what way do you have similar privileges as the person?

For alternative personas

- What experiences and needs does this person have that may become a problem or be seen as a disadvantage for being an entrepreneur?
- What would create a better situation for this person?
- What kinds of support mechanisms, resources or actions would have helped them?

Better stories

The second tool developed is the *better stories*. Better stories refer here to inspiring examples of working with promoting (gender) inclusiveness in tech entrepreneurship. In the workshop we depart from the concept of *Better stories* developed by researcher Dina Georgis to highlight promising practices that contribute to moving forward towards greater equality in particular contexts. Georgis writes “every story is the better story, or the best possible story we have invented to allow ourselves to go

⁵ Cooper, 1999; Källhammar & Wikberg Nilsson, 2012

⁶ The personas have been adapted to different national features and entrepreneurial contexts and are based on the data generated in the GENRE-project. The personalized approach in the persona methodology may also help to better understand how solutions to problems encountered by entrepreneurs may be addressed.

on living.”⁷ “Better” captures not the “best way to solve a particular challenge in a normative or definite sense, but rather, what is possible at a particular moment”.⁸ Better stories is thus not a search for a “perfect fix for all” but an invitation to identify, highlight and learn from the better stories to create more inclusive ecosystems emerging from different contexts, as well as an invitation to imagine even better stories to be further developed.

In the workshop examples from initiatives to promote an inclusive tech ecosystem in Ireland, Sweden, Norway and Israel are used as an inspiration and to facilitate a discussion on the challenges and opportunities of different types of initiatives and how they may be developed to become even better to create a better ecosystem.

Workshop outline

In this section the steps in the workshop will be explained. The steps are suggestions that can be adapted to fit the existing context as long as the existing aims of the workshop are fulfilled. The workshop is 3 hours including a break and consists of five sessions:

1. Introduction and warm up (30 min)
2. Personas and norm-reflexivity (30 min)
3. Better stories and inspiration (30 min)
Break (15 min)
4. Brainstorming and co-creation (45 min)
5. Wrap up and final reflections (30 min)

Facilitator team

The workshop needs a main facilitator and preferably a co-facilitator. The main facilitator leads the workshop, and the role of the co-facilitator is to assist the main facilitator as well as to keep track of the time, make sure that participants that have questions or want to make reflections are noticed (this is especially important if the workshop is made digitally).

Facilitators for the smaller group discussions should be assigned prior to the workshop. These will keep participants on track and take notes.

The documentation of the workshop is important and of special interest for the output of the workshop. We suggest a facilitator meeting, prior to the workshop to discuss how the workshop should be documented, by whom and in what way (see more below on the documentation).

Inviting participants

⁷ Georgis 2013, p.1

⁸ Georgis, 2013, p.2

We recommend that all participants are invited and for a next step make a request for a short bio or CV and to highlight their experience and role in working with the topic e.g.:

Can you please provide us now with a few lines on yourself (bio) to be included in the information to the participants including 1-3 key topics that you focus on in your work related to the topic?

This information can later be compiled and shared with the other participants together with contact details if participants agree to this.

For the participants that have accepted to join, the personas and better stories selected for the workshop should be sent out to the participant prior to the workshop so that they can familiarize themselves with the material that will be used during the workshop.

Setting up the workshop

The workshop can be done either in person or digitally. If it is done digitally, we recommend working in parallel with a digital meeting tool (e.g., Zoom/Teams/Skype) and a digital whiteboard (e.g., Miro, Mural) to gather the reflections made on digital “post-its” etc. If the workshop is done in person, it is good to organise spaces where participants can work together in smaller groups.

Detailed description of the workshop sessions

Session 1 - Introduction and warm up (30 min)

In the introduction the aim of the workshop will be explained together with the agenda and the concept of better stories. Existing inequalities in tech entrepreneurship ecosystems should be shortly introduced. The focus should be on the national and local contexts of the participants. The participants should thereafter introduce themselves (1 min each) e.g.

Who am I and what has been my own or my organization's better story?

The participants should be reminded that the workshop will be documented and to try to learn from and respect different viewpoints.

Session 2 - Personas and norm-reflexivity (30 min)

For the second session participants should be divided into smaller groups (approx. 5 participants per group, they can either stay or change groups also for session 3).

The personas that have been selected (max. 3 per group) should be either placed on the digital whiteboard or handed out for a short recap before the discussion starts. Let the participants discuss the personas by starting with the following questions:

Alternative personas:

- What experiences and needs do this person have that may become a problem or seen as a disadvantage for being an entrepreneur?
- What would create a better situation for this person?

- What kinds of support mechanisms, resources or actions would have helped them?

Norm-personas:

- What specific attributes does this person have that can give the person privileges as an entrepreneur that non-normative persons or groups lack?
- Optional: In what way do you have similar privileges as the person?

It is important to document what is being said and to make sure that all participants can share their reflections.

If the workshop is made in person, posters with the post-it notes can be placed on the wall so that participants can read the results from the other groups during the break.

Before the session ends the participants should be reminded to come back to the same group or change to a new group after the break (15 min).

Session 3 - Better stories and inspiration (30 min)

For session 3 the participants are gathered again in smaller groups, the same as before the break. The focus is the better stories that have been selected.

The participants should start with examining the table with different problems and solutions, the facilitator can go through them quickly to help the participants to get a sense of what solution has been imagined for different problems.

The better stories that have been selected (max. 3 per group) should be either placed on the digital whiteboard or handed out for a short recap before the discussion starts.

Let the participants look critically at the examples by discussing the following questions:

- What are their key advantages?
- What are the challenges?
- What results could they have?
- How might they be developed?

Before ending session 3, ask participants to summarise the 3-5 most pressing issues they think should be addressed to make the ecosystem more inclusive from different perspectives.

What is the problem? For whom is this a problem?

- 1)
- 2)
- 3)
- 4)
- 5)

Session 4 - Brainstorming and co-creation (45 min)

Session 4 starts in the bigger group (plenum). The problems summarised from the various groups are reported back to all. The problems that are similar or being reported by most groups are selected for the brainstorming and co-creation session. The participants are divided again into smaller groups, each group assigned with 1-3 problems and are asked to develop ideas on how to solve them.

1-2 ideas for how to solve the problems should be selected by the smaller group and developed further into concrete initiatives i.e., “better stories”, answering questions such as;

1. Impacts pursued?
2. Action description?
3. Target groups? Collaborators?
4. Key aspects to be included in a recommendation?
5. Open questions that need to be answered?

Session 5 - Wrap up and final reflections (30 min)

In the final session, which will be held in the bigger group (plenum), the initiatives and recommendations developed from all groups should briefly be summarised by the facilitators of the smaller groups. The participants should then be asked to give their view on:

- What actions do we want to pursue and what recommendations can we make?
- Key takeaways from the workshop from a personal point of view?

The workshop should be ended by explaining how the results of the workshop will be used for a publication to be shared to all participants encouraging further collaboration and development within the ecosystem.

The different steps of the workshop are summarized briefly in table 1.

Table 1. Outline for 3 hours workshop

SESSION	TIME	INPUT/TOOLS	OBJECTIVE	OUTPUT
Introduction and warm up	30 min	Participant profiles Existing challenges, nationally and locally (approx. 3 power points)	Familiarize participants with one another and with the approach. Question to participants: Who am I and what has been my own or my organization's better story? Introduce the context and basic facts, findings, and challenges	Examples of better stories, both individual and structural

<p>Personas and norm-reflexivity</p> <p>(Group work 1a)</p>	<p>30 min</p>	<p>Personas</p>	<p>Increase the participants understanding for differences in entrepreneurs' situations and prerequisites based on discussing:</p> <p>Alternative persona: What experiences and needs do this person have that may become a problem or seen as a disadvantage for being an entrepreneur?</p> <p>What would create a better situation for this person?</p> <p>What kinds of support mechanisms, resources or actions would have helped them?</p> <p>Norm-persona: What specific attributes does this person have that can give the person privileges as an entrepreneur that non-normative persons or groups lack?</p> <p>(In what way do you have similar privileges as the person?)</p>	<p>Critical learning/norm-reflexive ability</p>
<p>Break</p>	<p>5 min</p>			

<p>Better stories and inspiration</p> <p>(Group work 1b)</p>	<p>30 min</p>	<p>Better stories (15 min)</p> <p>Problems & Solutions table</p> <p>Problems (15 min)</p>	<p>Increase participants ability to critically assess and develop actions to promote inclusive entrepreneurship systems.</p> <p>Have participants look critically at the examples. What are their key advantages? What are the challenges? What results could they have? How might they be developed? (30 min)</p> <p>Before ending session 3 ask participants to summarize the 3-5 most pressing issues they think should be addressed to make the ecosystem more inclusive from different perspectives in the ecosystem- what is the problem? And who is this a problem for?</p>	<p>Inspiration and exchange of experiences</p> <p>Improved skill in critically assessing and designing initiatives to promote inclusive tech ecosystems</p>
<p>Brainstorming and co-creation</p>	<p>45 min</p>	<p>Question to guide the development</p>	<p>To facilitate the development of concrete actions to promote inclusive entrepreneurship systems</p> <p>Choose problems to work with</p> <p>Develop ideas on how to overcome barriers creating inequalities and how to enable a more inclusive entrepreneurship ecosystem</p> <p>Impacts pursued? Action description? Target groups? Collaborators? Key aspects to be included in a recommendation? Open questions that need to be answered?</p>	<p>Creation of concrete actions and recommendations</p>

Wrap up and final reflections	30 min	Summary made by facilitators	To spur further collaborations and concrete actions to be undertaken by actors Re-cap and priority discussions -What actions do we want to pursue and what recommendations can we make? Key takeaways	Inspirational publication for the ecosystem
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After the workshop

The outputs from the workshop are summed up. The facilitator team should meet again and decide how to proceed e.g., with documentation and initiatives to further spur collaboration.

Documentation

A crucial element of the workshop is the documentation. For this purpose, notetakers and observers should be assigned. The documentation should contain the main results from the workshop and the ideas for actions and recommendations developed. It can also include photos and inspiring quotes. Small interviews/telling quotes can be collected from the participants as well as additional information on already existing good practices. The results from the workshop as well as collected information are put together in an inspirational publication to be distributed “My Better Entrepreneurial Ecosystem”.

Recurring workshops

The workshop can be made as a recurring event in the ecosystem building further on the initiatives developed. New personas and promising practices can be developed and introduced highlighting different problems and solutions to overcome them. New better stories and personas can be developed to suit the context of the workshop.

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Appendix

Personas

Photo by Dnitriv Vecherka on Unplash

DECLAN, 26-year entrepreneur from Blackrock, Dublin

Interests: Collects Adidas trainers – so far 73 and counting.

Role model: Elon Musk

Norm-persona IRELAND

“A GO-GETTER WHO DOES NOT TAKE ‘NO’ FOR AN ANSWER”

About

Declan is a 26-year-old technology entrepreneur from the affluent area of Blackrock in south county Dublin. He was born into a family of Irish Catholic parents. Declan has demonstrated his competitive side from an early age having played many sports, including rugby and GAA football. Being over six feet tall, his height and athletic body shape communicate inner strength and bold confidence.

Dream big!

In terms of his plans and expectations, Declan dreams big. He wants to create and dominate markets. His wish is to leave behind him a legacy evident in a successful track record of starting profitable tech companies.

Entrepreneurship traits

Declan has always felt at home with technology. Started coding when he was fifteen, Declan also built a nuclear reactor with the assistance of his father in his own garden. In 2012 his parents bought him a Samsung Galaxy S3 with retrofittable wireless charging. This is when his journey into technology entrepreneurship begins.

After a computer Science BA degree at Trinity College Dublin, he found his niche in agile software development, which is a set of practices intended to improve the effectiveness of software development professionals, teams and organizations. Following several successful performances at student business plan competitions, his career quickly took off and he founded his own company to refine the product.

“You know, make your money and reinvest and it’s like this cycle. So, I don’t know, just to be able to exit and grow another company is what I would love to be able to do successfully and do more.”

Seema, 42-year-old plant-based food blogger from Rathmines, Ireland.

Interests: Photography

Role model: other working moms

Alternative persona IRELAND

“Everyone is using technology. Everyone can have an influence”

About

Seema is a first generation immigrant, having moved with her parents and siblings from India when she was just four years old. She completed her BA degree in Media at University College Dublin, and she married her long-term partner soon following her graduation. Together they have three children, one of whom has autism and requires additional care. Seema’s husband Sai, Indian by descent as well, holds a managerial role in a Dublin-based IT company.

Make tech gender inclusive!

She wants to challenge the concept of technology entrepreneurship to make it more inclusive of those who do not have a background in technology. She is however acutely aware that women in tech entrepreneurship need to have high levels of self-confidence and self-efficacy to stand side-by-side with men.

You know, we go off, we have children, we get distracted, we have other commitments. When they [investors] give you their money, they want blood, sweat and tears, they don’t just want your talent, they want your hours, and no female wants to sign up to being a slave to that.

Entrepreneurship traits

Seema is candid about the struggles experienced by working mums, and female entrepreneurs specifically. Her motivation to build a business that centers around food came out of necessity - feeding her growing family. She developed a state-of-art website. Soon her mouth-watering recipes and impeccable photography was featured in Marie Claire, Cosmopolitan, Elle and Huffington Post. Her first cookbook became a #1 Best Seller on Amazon.

She is critical of the funding landscape in the ecosystem and investors’ reluctance to acknowledge that women and men entrepreneurs operate differently due to their different personal responsibilities. She reflects on the pressure experienced by female entrepreneurs to deliver an impeccable product and impeccable physical appearance.

John, 40-year entrepreneur from Stockholm

Interests: skiing, surfing, running

Role model: Jacob De Geer

Norm-persona Sweden

“I prefer working with women ”

About

John is a 40-year-old entrepreneur with a business school degree working with IT. He has lived in the US for a year and worked in various ski-resorts in the French alps. Currently he and his family are living in Spain, taking a year off the busy life in the Swedish capital. He calls himself an “entrepreneur in digital financial solutions”, having co-founded several startups already. His kids, 3 and 5 years old, are doing all sorts of sports after day-care, mainly soccer and dancing.

Entrepreneurship traits

John worked in the IT-sector for several years, together with his 3 male friends Tommy, Walter and Daniel developed several niche solutions for the financial business online trading. With an eye both for IT and business, their start-up companies will hopefully become known as reliable, innovative and profitable over time. He hopes that their digital solutions will make trading even more easily accessible and cheaper than it is today.

Individuals, not gender

John dislikes talking about gender, he prefers talking about individuals. For John, gender inequality is mainly a generational thing that will pass, it is problem that will be solved over time. John prefers working with women – even though his current team happens to be all male. It’s also about risk taking being hard wired into the male DNA. John finds himself “bothered” by specific support for women since he finds it discriminatory to men.

John says he has the “perfect team” already in place, their main challenge is to attract investors and to convince them their IT-solution is the Game changer John, and his team believes it is. Hopefully their start-up will pay off well so that he and his co-founders can “pay it forward” by making their own investments sometimes in the future.

“I am all for 50/50 representation, but in male dominated sectors like the finance world we cannot take 50/50 from a 20/80 pot.”

Stefan, 56-year entrepreneur from Gothenburg

Interests: his family and IT

Role model: Greta Thunberg

Alternative persona Sweden

“Is kind of the norm, that you are supposed to bend the rules”

About

Stefan has an international professional background, having worked in Asia, Europe and now Sweden. His wife is Swedish, and they have 2 kids – both girls. He has a background in engineering and have worked in many projects involving typically male dominated sectors. He is a fast talker, a person with lots on his mind, and who says he loves to work. Tech-startups has become a way to let off steam and find new ways of fixing problems.

Challenges

Product development and financing is not Stefan’s main challenges. Being a father of two young daughters made him aware of gender inequality in society at large and in his own fields of expertise such as IT – including tech startups. In Stefan’s view, his main activity is to negotiate with venture capitalists, who operates in a very masculine way of evaluating funders by going out drinking late in the evening.

Open-source4all!

Stefan works in a research environment where spin-offs are encouraged, even expected. It is easy to get support from the university to get started. For Stefan, to produce applications that is shared under open-source models is the way forward – IT solutions for education should be equally available. This stance is however met with resistance, both from the incubator and from own team members at times - it is much harder to make money on open-source applications compared to licensed ones.

Start-ups by non-normative folks is at risk in a competitive, masculine start-up culture. Stefan thinks the norm is still men like Elon Musk, Bill Gates and Peter Thiel, all very well spoken and friendly, but also very aggressive – like the most well-known entrepreneur off all, Donald Trump. In the end, this means that women - including his daughters - do not fit this male norm, they have less of a choice compared with the men in the incubator and when seeking investments.

So, the main challenge was how to deal with this as a start-up – should one object or not?

Petter, 38-year entrepreneur from Oslo

Interests: family, sports, running, skiing, finance, watch sports

Role model: Erik Fossum Færevaaag, Disruptive tech

Norm persona Norway

“To be honest, I haven’t reflected much on gender equality before I became a dad”.

About

Petter is civil engineer from Oslo. Living in a house together with his wife Iselin and their two children, aged one and three. He has an active lifestyle, and likes to go running or skiing, and he is in good physical shape. The family has access to a mountain cottage, where they often go during the weekends. He enjoys spending time with the family. Petter has a sporty clothing style but makes sure to put on a nice suit when there are important meetings, or when presenting for potential investors.

On gender-equality

With a daughter and a son, gender equality is important. He and his wife are trying to share domestic work. However, they have both decided that he should focus on the start-up, and since Iselin also wants to spend more time with the children, she is the one who takes most of the parental leave. Regarding gender equality in the start-up environment, he says that it is important that everyone is given equal opportunities.

Challenges and opportunities

Petter and his close friend from University Eirik, developed a product prototype and set up a business two years ago. He is genuinely interested in developing the product, which has the potential to influence the sector and become a success. They are both hardworking and diligent, and willing to give 100% for the start-up. If everything goes well, the start-up will be profitable within one or two years, and the founders believe that it has great potential to go global within the sector they are operating. The main challenge has been to get investors, which is now solved, and the two co-founders are still majority owners. There has also been some challenges in finding the right suppliers for material and location for production.

Today there are no formal barriers for women, I guess women are more risk averse, and are less interested in technology, I think that explains the low proportion of women in tech. But I would be happy to see more women in technology sectors!

Anita, 56-year entrepreneur from Bergen

Interests: events, her company, her children

Role model: health care workers

Photo by iStockphoto.com/Sarah Manganoni https://www.pexels.com/photo/woman-sitting-white-laptop-3251828/

Alternative persona Norway

“We have everything against us. Investors do not realize that this has the potential to become very profitable!”

About

Anita is a cheerful and warm person, who is easy to talk to, quick in making new contacts. She dresses in a relaxed, but feminine style. She is divorced and has three grown up children. For several years, she was staying at home, when the children were small. She has an education as nurse, and has been working with different things within health, both in public and private sector. Anita has always loved to work with people.

On gender-equality

She talks about how gender is formed from a young age, and how important it is to encourage both girls and boys to try out different activities, sports and subjects. She also highlights that the entrepreneurial environment must be inclusive for all, in relation to gender, ethnicity and age. But one should also try to lower the barriers for those who cannot work 24/7, independent on if it is due to family situation or due to physical abilities.

Motivations

Anita often get ideas on how to improve different things in the health sector. Her start-up is based on a product that will promote physical activity among old people with disabilities. She believes that physical activity is important throughout the whole life and argues that physical activity is extremely important for our mental health. They are aiming to primarily reach the Norwegian market, potentially European market.

The start-up is funded by Anita and her friend Jorunn, who is a medical doctor with focus on elderly care. The challenge has been to convince investors. They have used their own savings, worked on their spare time and used some public grants, but are now in need of private investments to take the next step.

“We are two women, who are not so young, and we have developed a product within the health sector, targeting old, disabled people, who are low prioritized in our society.”

Yoav, 45-year-old tech entrepreneur from Herzliya, Tel Aviv

Interests: family life, hiking, biking and enjoying nature

Role models: his father, defence tech engineer, and his mother, private clinic owner

Norm persona Israel
“Taking timeout for my children gave me perspective”

About

Yoav is a tech entrepreneur, Jewish and of European origin. Yoav was married to Shoshana who whom he has three children aged 10, 12, 15. They each have apartments in a suburb of Tel Aviv, Herzliya, considered one of the main technology hubs in the center of Israel. After graduating from high school Yoav was chosen to serve in a technological intelligence unit of the Israeli army. Upon his return he received several job-offers in high-tech and specifically cyber companies, through friends who also served in the same intelligence army unit.

Single fathering

As a single father, Yoav was “forced” to take timeout for his children and take over full responsibility during his parental shifts. This experience gave him insights to the challenge of juggling business and family. His ex-wife held an executive management position in a large multinational and this too helped him understand the challenges that are typically faced by working women.

Entrepreneurship traits

While working at the multinational cyber company Yoav and his friend developed an idea in their spare time which management did not consider it in the scope of interest of the company. Therefore, he and his good friend left and decided to launch their own startup company. The startup took 200% of his time and attention, and it was at this stage that his marriage fell apart.

Yoav and his partner had many funding opportunities due to the fact that cyber is the hot topic amongst the many international investment funds active in Israel. Nonetheless, they chose to initially go with angels in order to avoid deluding equity at an early stage. As often the case for Israeli startups, the fact that Yoav and his partner had a wide national and international network, was an asset.

“In order to gain traction, we had to earn acceptance and be allowed to do a project for a customer overseas.”

Yael, 40-year-old female serial entrepreneur from Haifa

Interests: family life, cooking

Role models: women living with cancer

Alternative persona Israel
“I want to help women fighting cancer”

About

Yael was born on a Kibbutz in the Northern periphery of Israel. She served in a technology-based unit in the army that provided intensive computer training as part of her army service. She is married to a university professor, and they live together with their two children in a rural settlement close to Haifa. They spend their time looking for activities entertaining their small children and meeting with extended family on a regular basis - the Shabbat dinner in particular. Part of her partners family is living in the USA, so they travel there yearly.

Targeting breast cancer

Yael obtained a PhD in medical research. While working in a laboratory with a group of distinguished researchers at the Technion in Haifa, she developed a testing mechanism for breast cancer research which allowed the lab to advance their research beyond expectations. Yael realized that the testing mechanism had commercial value and applied for and was accepted for a patent.

Entrepreneurship traits

Upon acceptance of the patent Yael decided to leave the research lab and set up a startup based on commercializing the product idea. Even though she had an impressive career in terms of army service, higher education with honors at a prestigious institution and a rich industrial research experience, it became obvious that alone she would be extremely to obtain entrance into the startup ecosystem.

When applying for programs of funding's it was constantly suggested that she add a male figurehead to her founding team. In addition, when attending funding pitches Yael often found that the audience would be more attentive to a male presenter even if he was less knowledgeable than herself. Being the consummate professional that she is, she did not allow herself to abandon her desire to help society and specifically women with cancer.

“The incubator provided a comfortable environment but did not assist in obtaining additional funding – I ‘needed’ a man for that.”

Summing up and key reflection points

This exercise has asked you to reflect upon norm and alternative personas. By doing so we have encouraged you to consider privileges associated with the norm persona and potential problems and disadvantages following with the alternative persona. Here we ask you to write down, compare and reflect further on your findings:

Key reflection points:

- Please summarize the attributes that give the norm persona privileges as an entrepreneur that non-normative persons or groups lack?
- Please summarize the key experiences and needs of the alternative persona that may become a problem or be seen as a disadvantage for being an entrepreneur.
- Is there something you find particularly problematic, if so, what would that be?
- How would you suggest this problem be addressed? By whom?
- How would your findings be relevant for your own organization or in your profession?

Better stories from four countries

In the following section, we will introduce previous and ongoing responses to the gender imbalance – initiatives for a more inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystem. In doing so, we exemplify what has been done and invite you as a reader to imagine better ways of addressing this issue from where you stand. First, a note on concepts. There is a large skepticism within the scholarly field towards possibilities to find universal (one size fits all) and ready-to-apply “best practices” regarding change management in general and equality issues in particular. Putting “best” or “evidence-based” as a label on a practice might even lead to unwanted effects, an uncritical acceptance that may lead to unnoticed harmful effects and prevent further development and analysis. The concept *Better stories* is offered as an alternative term to best practice.

Below are examples identified as *Better stories*. We have provided two or three from each country: Ireland, Sweden, Norway and Israel. For each of these cases, you may want to consider what makes these *Better stories*? What can you take with you as inspiration to your organisation? What could be improved? These questions can also be discussed and developed further in a workshop.

Ireland

Enterprise Ireland Action Plan for Women in Business

Enterprise Ireland is a government organisation that works in partnership with Irish enterprises to help them start, grow, innovate and win export sales in global markets. Enterprise Ireland provides a wide range of services including funding support, export assistance, support to develop competitiveness, incentives to stimulate in-company research and development, and assistance with making connections and introductions to customers overseas.

Background

Since 2011, Enterprise Ireland has become increasingly aware of the small number of female-led startups in the Irish ecosystem. Specifically, only 7% of startups at that time had a female lead. Enterprise Ireland decided to address this identified gender gap, and a number of long and short-term initiatives resulted from that decision. These activities resulted in an increase from 7% of female-led startups in 2011 to 23% in 2020. More recently, Enterprise Ireland has decided to take a broader approach in how it addresses the underrepresentation of women in enterprise, which has witnessed an expansion in its objectives. The Action Plan for Women in Business is a comprehensive six-year action plan launched in January 2020, which aims to further increase the participation of women in entrepreneurship and business leadership.

Action plan

The overarching aim of the Action Plan is to drive Ireland's economic success by optimising skills and talent through increasing the participation of women in entrepreneurship and business leadership.

The strategy is underpinned by four key objectives:

- To increase the number of women-led companies growing internationally
- To increase the number of women in middle and senior management and leadership roles in Irish companies
- To increase the number of women becoming entrepreneurs
- To increase the number of women-led startups with high growth potential.

Enterprise Ireland highlights the deployment of gender lens in its work as an achievement in itself. By including this strategy in the commercial evaluation of projects and funding application process, Enterprise Ireland makes a statement about its commitment to gender diversity to its external partners.

Change strategy

Key strengths: Consciousness-raising around the existing gender imbalance in the enterprise, as well as an emphasis on the significant benefits to companies that implement gender diversity in senior positions. These include increased profitability, increased ability to attract and retain talent, greater creativity, innovation and openness, enhanced company reputation, and better ability to gauge consumer interest and demand. Another strength is that it focuses on increasing the number of women in senior management positions, 80% of female founders come from senior management roles. Therefore, an increase in the number of women in senior management positions will translate into an increase in the number of female-led startups.

Key challenges: Covid-19 pandemic inevitably had an impact on the delivery of the Action Plan. Enterprise Ireland however continued to move forward with the Action Plan despite these challenges.

Learn more

www.enterprise-ireland.com/en/

AwakenHub

AwakenHub was founded in 2020 by four female entrepreneurs following an identified need for an all island of Ireland community for women founders. The aim of the initiative is to change the landscape for female founders, and to open up the investor community for women across both North and South Ireland. AwakenHub welcomes all female founders/entrepreneurs.

Background

AwakenHub is a result of conversations between several Irish female entrepreneurs about bringing together their work in order to support female founders. The overarching aim of the initiative is to change the landscape for women founders and to open up the investor community for women across Ireland. The founders identified three specific issues that led them to establish the organisation. Firstly, they anticipated the 'great resignation' following the Covid-19 pandemic, an opportunity for women to review their work-life balance, maybe realize a business idea they had for a long time, and yet never had an opportunity to test it. Another motivation was to help existing female entrepreneurs that had been struggling due to the impact of the pandemic and may have lost their income. Finally, the founders were acutely aware of the difficulties that women experience in accessing funding resources, incubators and accelerators.

Objective and strategy for change

The core objective of AwakenHub is to support and amplify women founders. The organisation molds its activities based on the feedback from its members - established and aspiring female founders. It provides women with an opportunity to learn about the world of investment and funding streams, build their business profile and grow their professional network. As of August 2021 AwakenHub gathers over 1100 members, overwhelmingly women. Irish businesswomen who have emigrated also make part of this community, alongside women that exited their businesses and female founders from a corporate background.

Since its launch in July 2020 AwakenHub has facilitated a number of events for its members. The topics included becoming investor ready and raising investment, raising seed funding, building successful investor-entrepreneur relationship, building social networks, storytelling in business, business pivoting, international business development and negotiation skills. AwakenHub also manages a private by-invitation-only Slack group for women founders, which is a space where female founders can seek advice and support from other members, experienced women entrepreneurs (so called 'Big Sisters'), investors and company builders.

Strength and challenges

Key strengths: Due to utilising online platforms exclusively, AwakenHub has enabled women from all parts of the Republic and Northern Ireland to join. The founders emphasise that AwakenHub is a community rather than a network, and the founders are also clear about the 'no hugging the room' policy, which prevents one person from dominating the conversation and it enables inclusion and participation of all members. The founders emphasize that they manage these relationships very carefully to justify and safeguard mutual trust.

Key challenges: The founders of AwakenHub described the founding journey as a 'nightmare'. Even though other organisations in the ecosystem are well supported by the Government, yet the AwakenHub has not received financial support. However, the founders are keen to continue this dialogue, especially having secured the financial support from Rethink Ireland. Since January 2021 the AwakenHub started to charge for participation in their online events.

Learn more

www.awakenhub.com

Going for Growth

Going for Growth is an initiative funded by Enterprise Ireland and KPMG that aims to support female entrepreneurs to realise their growth aspiration. Participants are offered a learning environment with a peer-led approach based on the shared experiences of both a Lead Entrepreneur and other participants on the programme. Going for Growth has supported over 800 female entrepreneurs in the past thirteen years.

Background

Going for Growth targets ambitious female entrepreneurs across all sectors who are located in the Republic of Ireland. Suitable applicants for the programme are owner managers of a business, wherein the founder is a major shareholder and key influencer. It is founded on the work of Paula Fitzsimons and Prof Colm O’Gorman from Dublin City University Business School who began their cooperation on the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM), which provides information on the number of male and female early-stage entrepreneurs. GEM was conducted on an annual basis, which enabled tracking year-over-year progress in Ireland and comparing the outcomes with a range of other countries. The initial GEM findings suggested that for every two men there was one woman setting up the business. The National Development Plan (NDP) Gender Equality Unit in the then Department of Justice, Equality and Law Reform became familiar with these findings and conversations began as to what could be done about the gender gap in the context of startups.

Initiative

Going for Growth has developed into a suite of complementary initiatives, which provides support to female entrepreneurs appropriate to their stage of development. This includes Starting Strong, where innovative early-stage entrepreneurs have generated some sales but in general have less than two years’ revenue, Going for Growth, for entrepreneurs who have been trading for at least two years; and Continuing the Momentum, for those who have successfully completed a cycle of Going for Growth and are a member of the Community and wish to drive further growth within their business and would welcome the support of the round tables to help them do so. In all aspects there is strong emphasis on achieving growth.

Specifically, the Going for Growth Roundtables gather Lead Entrepreneurs, who volunteer about three hours of their time on a monthly basis, and a small group of female business owners and/or managers. The roundtable sessions explore a series of relevant topics related to business growth. In that process, the Lead Entrepreneurs act as role models - they provide guidance, act as a sounding board, support the participants with building their own networks, and facilitate peer-to-peer learning.

Strength and challenges

Key strengths: the approach is anchored in Fitzsimons’ awareness of the lack of self-confidence amongst female entrepreneurs, which may act as a self-imposing barrier to growing a business. Programmes tailored for women founders need to build women’s self-confidence and therefore help them realise what they can achieve. In that context, Going for Growth supports women in strengthening their self-confidence through the work of Lead Entrepreneurs, who demonstrate what is possible to achieve by sharing their own experiences in a collaborative nature. Moreover, the structured nature of the programme makes it possible to measure its effectiveness.

Key challenges: There had been no significant challenges encountered since the programme was set up. Going for Growth had a clear mission from the onset, and the policy developments in Ireland supported the development of the initiative.

Learn more

www.goingforgrowth.com

Israel

רשות החדשנות Israel Innovation Authority

Preferential Financing for Women, Ultra-Orthodox, and Minorities

Israel Innovation Authority is an independent publicly funded agency, responsible of Israel’s innovation policy. Its role is to cultivate and develop the innovation resource in Israel while creating relevant infrastructures and strengthening the structural foundations that support the entire knowledge-based industry.

Background

In 2017-2018 only 8% of technological initiatives in Israel were founded by women, and only 10% of applications to the Innovation Authority Startup route came from women-led startups. Leading the Innovation Authority to identify women as an underrepresented group that should be incorporated into the preferential funding program, in order to increase the number of female tech entrepreneurs in Israel and thus fully exhaust the innovation potential of different sectors in Israel. According to the Innovation Authority, female entrepreneurs experience additional obstacles to those encountered by male entrepreneurs, namely – a difficulty in raising initial (seed and pre-seed) investments.

Aims and activities

The grant program for female-led start-ups aims to minimise the gender gap in Israel’s high-tech ecosystem by helping women entrepreneurs meet basic challenges such as funding and networking with potential investors. With the new initiative, the IIA hopes to double the number of women it supports within 2 years.

Women-led start-ups will be eligible for grants for up to 75% of their R&D funding in the 1st year of the programme and 70% in the 2nd year, with caps of ILS 2.5 million (around €75 570) in the 1st year and ILS 4.5 million (around €1.22 million) in the 2nd. In addition, the IIA plans to launch a programme to give women access to all the support tools available through the organisation. The preferential funding program strives to “encourage technological innovation with the aim of strengthening and advancing the Israeli economy” via support of start-up companies owned by female and/or ultra-Orthodox and/or minorities entrepreneurs.

Strength and challenges

Key strengths: targets population groups whose members have difficulties entering the ecosystem since they are lacking networks and resources. For these groups to obtain funding is the main obstacle and the scheme targets this obstacle.

Key challenges: founders can get the same amount of money through this fund or by entering an incubator. Many chose this fund since they do not have to relinquish equity as they are required to do upon entering an incubator. However, entering an incubator provides resources not afforded to the same extent through the grant.

Learn more

<https://innovationisrael.org.il/en/>

Advanced mentoring programs and communities for women

"Ha'Meitzot" (The female accelerator)
 Dr. Tali Feldman-Sivan – a successful entrepreneur who sold her startup for 290 million dollars, and Hana Rado – an Israeli operations expert and social business entrepreneur, initiated "Ha'Meitzot" program, launched in 2021.

Context

"Hameizot" is- an accelerator program dedicated for promoting female founders in Israel. Their vision is to increase the number of women establishing and leading start-up companies in Israel. The program is led by Supersonas', an Israeli social organisation, established in 2015 by Hana Rado.

Program

The program is built of 10 weekly four-hours meetings, including methodological lectures, professional lectures, pitching training and presentation refinement. The sessions will be divided into a methodological lecture, a lecture by a professional lecturer and an investor panel. Each start-up will present her startup idea and receive feedback until a final presentation with the aim of giving tools to build a professional investor presentation.

The main idea of the program is twofold: to set up a network of women technological entrepreneurs to counter the existing "white Jewish male" network which is based very much on similar army experience and rather exclusive (with women and minorities finding it more difficult to enter). Secondly, Dr. Feldman-Sivan believes that women need more time than men and are less confident as to their human capital and expertise, therefore mentoring in small groups with a high level of solidarity is productive and will foster the women's path to setting up their startup.

The vision

The vision of the program is to increase the number of female founders - establishing and leading startup companies.

The program agenda encompasses:

- A diverse program - covering all the areas of expertise required to lead a startup company
- Professional guidance by an experienced team
- Assistance in building an initial business plan
- Business Model refinement
- Building a work plan and setting milestones for development and fund raising
- Develop a professional investor presentation that will be presented at the end of the program to an investor panel
- Exposure to an extensive local and global network of potential investors and professionals
- Support of the Supersonas Community - a community of 3,000 Israeli business and professional women
- On the professional's side- the program allows exposure to potential customers and gives extensive PR

The initiative run on voluntary basis with self paying participants.

Learn more

www.supersonas.com/en/

Norway

#huninvesterer

DNB (Den Norske Bank)
 DNB is the biggest finance corporation in Norway. It was founded in 1822 and is operating in all of Norway.

The Norwegian government is the main owner (34 %). In total, DNB has around 2.1 million private customers, and 232 000 business customers. Number of employees is over 9000.

Background

As one of the main commercial players in the finance sector, DNB is also working with CSR in different ways. The project in focus here is called #huninvesterer, meaning 'she invests', which is focusing on increasing the gender balance in investments. The background is the prevailing gender gap when looking at both private investments and savings, and DNB argues that more knowledge is needed to close this gap. DNB is aiming to reach Norwegian women, and to spread knowledge and inspiration about savings and investments. The main platform for the project is a Facebook-group, #huninvesterer, which started in September 2019. Since the start of the Facebook-group in September 2019, it has grown to include more than 22 000 members. There have also been several physical meetings where women around Norway have been invited to participate, to get inspiration, share knowledge and to network.

Change strategy

The strategy is to increase the gender balance in savings and investments in Norway, by changing women's attitudes regarding private economy, savings and investments. This is done by participation in an active forum on social media, the Facebook group. There is no long-term commitment by any part.

Aim

The aim is to reach (mainly) women in Norway with knowledge and inspiration regarding private economy, private savings and investments, not the least for private pension savings. The idea is that anyone who is a member in the Facebook-group can bring up discussion topics, ask questions and reply. There are also some experts from DNB connected to the Facebook-group, who assist in answering questions. They only touch on topics in a general way, and no specific advice for savings/trading is allowed. As part of the project, DNB also arranges seminars with physical meetings every now and then. This takes place in different parts of Norway and has been very popular. The events have been based on inspirational talks, but also for building networks for women with interest for private economy.

Strength and challenges

A key strength with #huninvesterer is that it is cheap to administrate and has the potential to reach a large number of women. It is an easy way to increase awareness about investments and other related topics among women. It is fairly easy to highlight good examples and provide information.

Learn more

Huninvesterer.no

STARTUP LAB

Going for Growth

StartupLab has been operating since 2012 and have supported more than 400 technology startups since then. In 2021, more than 110 members are connected to the tech incubators in Oslo and Bergen. The incubator highlights the community itself as the strongest asset, including the alumni, mentors, industry experts and corporate partners within and around the incubator.

Background

The incubator has previously seen a very low number of women in the founding teams. The last three years, there has been a strategy in the incubator to increase gender balance. Between 2016 and 2019, the female tenants rate went from 8% to 27%. Incubator manager Sonia Bains: *It is a little too easy to say that they [women entrepreneurs] are not out there, but they may be operating a bit more under the radar or in other nodes of the network than we are in.* "Show, don't tell" was the basis, where incubator management started with their own employees and partners to increase gender balance. The overall goal was to reach 40% gender balance at the end of 2020.

Strategy for change

StartupLab's strategy builds on working from within the own organization, to change the mindset and to become more gender aware in relation to stakeholders around the incubator. This has also meant that they put extra effort in finding female investors to cooperate with. Starting with themselves and the incubator, then involving stakeholders around the incubator, gives an impact on the ecosystem itself.

The "show, don't tell" was the basis for their strategy, which means the gender balance strategy has not been turned into a specific activities, it has been mainstreamed into the general incubator strategy. There hasn't been any specific training for the staff, other than what they have learned from other actors. There hasn't been any specific information material or communication activities. This is all in line with the approach to 'show, don't tell'.

There has been an increased proportion of female tenants among the founding teams in the incubator – from 8% in 2016 to 27% in 2020. Additionally, the proportion of women in the incubator management and in the networks surrounding the incubator, such as investors, had also increased.

Strength and challenges

Key strengths: StartupLab's strategy builds on gender awareness within the organization itself, and that this awareness should permeate all stakeholder relations as well as incubator tenants. Since it is built on change that comes from within the incubator, it has potential to really make a long-lasting effect, both within the incubator and in relation to different stakeholders (including to involve more female investors). Further, by focusing on the approach "show, don't tell", the incubator builds legitimacy and can potentially become a role model for other incubators/actors in the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Key challenges: A challenge is that it takes time and that there is a lot of resistance built into the ecosystem. It has also been a challenge to balance between trying to be gender aware and gender inclusive, and at the same time having to say no to entrepreneurs with high potential.

Learn more

www.goingforgrowth.com

Program for Regional R&D and Innovation (VRI)

The Research Council of Norway works to promote research and innovation of high quality and relevance and to generate knowledge in priority areas to enable Norway to deal with key challenges to society and the business sector.

Background

Policy makers striving for regional prosperity and economic growth have been moving towards more system-oriented focus in order to support entrepreneurship. In order to improve entrepreneurial ecosystems, governments have introduced various measures and support schemes. The overall objective of the VRI program was to generate knowledge about innovation processes in the regions, enhance cooperation on innovation among regional actors and promote research-based innovation in working life.

Since it has also been acknowledged that entrepreneurial ecosystems are gender biased and that women may represent underexploited entrepreneurial opportunities, gender balance was introduced as a goal in the VRI program after it started.

Aim and activities

The aim of the program was to increase awareness of gender balance among regional innovation ecosystem actors by introducing a goal on gender balance and requiring an action plan for gender balance in an ecosystem development program – where regional ecosystem development projects were funded. The goal was further to strive for gender balanced participation in the program at all levels and in all key processes.

The VRI program was established in 2007 for a ten-year period, divided into three program periods. The program consisted of two main types of activities, regional collaborative projects and innovation-oriented research projects. The collaborative projects were to ensure effective knowledge flow between the different actors (companies, research groups, public sector) and thereby strengthen regional innovation systems.

Change strategy

In the beginning of the VRI program, there was no specific focus on gender. After the first year of the first program period (2007-2010) a gender mainstreaming policy was introduced, in the second program period (2011-2013), the focus was directed to diversity, where women's engagement is understood as one out of several sources of diversity. In the third program period (2014-2016) the gender perspective is stated in more explicit terms. Thus, the gender balance policy changed over the three project periods, from a counting focused gender mainstreaming policy (first period) to a diversity focused gender mainstreaming policy (second period) and finally towards a gender-balance focused mainstreaming policy (third period).

Strength and challenges

The key factor for succeeding with implementing public gender policies that are targeting a whole entrepreneurial ecosystem is that there are some actors who already show gender awareness and are 'prepared' to work with activities aiming to improve gender balance. The results from the VRI program varied among the 15 regional ecosystems involved. If there are no endogenous factors within the entrepreneurial ecosystem that are promoting improved gender balance, it can be very challenging to reach results by implementing exogenous policies. An experience learned from the VRI program was that most entrepreneurial ecosystems are reluctant for changes.

Learn more

www.forskningradet.no/en

Sweden

Equal opportunities for innovation: Who, how and what get financing?

Vinnova is a state agency that promotes innovation. Vinnova's mission is to strengthen Sweden's ability to innovate in order to contribute to sustainable growth. Vinnova's task is to promote sustainable growth by financing needs-motivated research and the development of effective innovation systems.

Inclusive innovation support

KTH Royal Institute of Technology is one of Europe's leading technical and engineering universities. KTH is Sweden's largest technical research and learning institution. At the center of entrepreneurship is **KTH Innovation**, providing support for new ideas from students, researchers, and employees.

Background

In VINNOVA's instructions from the government, it is stated that the agency should integrate an equality perspective into the agency's activities and promote gender equality in the distribution of funds for research and innovation. The agency shall also work to include gender and/or gender equality perspectives in the projects that are financed, where applicable. To do this, the agency work actively with gender mainstreaming. There has been several notable results from the work. From 2015 when the work started the number of women project managers has increased approximately 10% (from approx. 30% to 40%) and the total distribution of funding is now within the 40-60% span and thus in line with the national gender equality objectives.

Who, how and what?

VINNOVA has worked with three main areas linked to who, how and what. **Who** - includes work around who is being financed. The focus is on the project team and the gender composition, such as how many women and men who are project leaders, the time and resources allocated to different positions and tasks in the project from a gender perspective. All projects must have an action plan for gender equality.

Concerning **what**, which is the latest stage in the development at the agency, it relates to the aims and the methodology of the project where the ambition is that a gender perspective should be incorporated if it is relevant. The applicant has to answer whether it is or not and give a motivation in both cases. In relation to setting up the call, the responsible call manager at VINNOVA gets help to incorporate gender related topics and criteria if needed.

The **how** dimension - has two parts. The first is that the applications are set up in a way so that it gives a good basis for assessing the gender aspects, the second is that the review committee has an equal representation and are trained in gender bias, they also have the competence to assess how gender is relevant to the subject area of the project.

Strength and challenges

Four key strengths: 1) gender expertise "in-house" at Vinnova, 2) the aims and objectives are supported in the organisation, 3) committed colleagues, and finally 4) that a support function was set up and dialogue initiated at an early stage.

Key challenges: to move beyond counting numbers and ticking boxes to really understand the essence in the measures. One example is variations detected in how applicants understands and provide answers for different questions related to gender and it takes a lot of gender training and awareness raising to support the change envisioned. Another problem that has been highlighted in the evaluations made is that many projects tend to lose the gender perspective over time. This is something that the agency is currently working on to address.

Learn more

www.vinnova.se
Learn how gender matters: Zero Vibration injuries (link)

Background

The initiative started as a project in 2016 and 2017 with the overall aim of getting more women to use KTH Innovation's offer. With the help of knowledge acquisition, competence development and analysis, the incubator worked to strengthen the capacity to handle diversity issues, and the project resulted in conclusions about measures that should give more women idea bearers in the long run. Since the initial project several different approaches and measures have been applied. A strong underlying ambition is that the work should not become a "pink project" meaning a short-term initiative which seeks to help women overcome barriers as a separate and complementary activity e.g., to teach women how to "pitch as a man". Instead, the work have been directed to address underlying gender norms in the everyday work of the incubator, to "turn the focus inwards" i.e., rather than to address women as the "problem".

Methods and approaches

KTH Innovation works with several different approaches. One is to ensure that all, both staff and participants, have knowledge about gender related inequalities and risk for bias in various parts of the entrepreneurial process. For example, the risk of applying different implicit standards for women and men.

Another is the emergency brake that should be used that if the gender representation in a start-up is to unbalanced (different targets for different activities). Since this "rule" was introduced the gender representation quickly rose and the rule never had to be put in action.

The addressing of underlying gendered norms of technological entrepreneurship has resulted in a specific approach where women are not lifted for their uniqueness or as role models, rather their participation as part of the mainstream group of entrepreneurs is emphasized.

KTH Innovation makes the incubator activities inclusive by adjusting activities from competition-type of activities that attracts mostly men to those emphasizing community building.

Strength and challenges

Key strengths: Its long-term commitment provides a stable platform for change. With the positive feedback and attention for the initiative comes not only pride, but also gives legitimacy for its importance. To measure and monitor the progress is a key for success.

Key challenges: It is not enough to only work with your own organization even if it is a necessary step, to collaborate with other actors in the ecosystem is key - but also a challenge. There are also a risk for set-backs if not keeping a focus on moving forward by making initiatives like these part of the regular organization, including taking necessary steering decisions on a strategic level. Outreach in women dominated sectors are important to recruit broader and scrutinizing the internal support functions to avoid gender bias.

Learn more

www.kth.se

Gender Contact Point

The initiative seeks to advance knowledge on how to promote gender equality in business through collaborative and action-oriented research and development work. It is a "gateway" for companies to get in contact with gender researchers at the University with the aim to participate in collaborative projects and develop the business.

Background

Gender Contact Point was initiated by Luleå University of Technology in 2014, in order to create a cohesive platform for university-society cooperation on gender equality about business models, recruitment and innovation, in SMEs from the ICT industry and municipalities. The initiative was preceded by several individual projects on the same topic, where university researchers cooperated with industrial companies as well as organizations from the public and non-profit sectors. Gender Contact Points have resulted in both new research and development efforts in the companies that have been involved. The university have also integrated gender studies to a higher degree in the technical programmes offered to students.

Aim to enforce inclusive growth

"The aim [of Gender Contact Point] is to enforce smart, sustainable and inclusive growth through gender-aware business models and innovations. This is achieved through joint learning by researchers from the university and employees from the companies and municipalities – using and producing both scientific and practical knowledge and measures. The learning takes place through joint development, tests and conceptualization of gender-aware business models and innovations. It further takes place through activities for knowledge dissemination, consultation on gender mainstreaming in other processes for university-society cooperation, and additional efforts."

"The identified incentive for the companies and municipalities to engage in the platform is to access scientific knowledge and methods for gender mainstreaming in their organizations and operations. Gender Smart Arena involves researchers from the university with expertise in gender studies and adjacent disciplines. Their identified incentive to engage in the platform is to gain insights into the companies' and municipalities' preconditions and challenges in regard to gender equality and university-society cooperation, as a basis for scientific advancement in gender studies and participatory research."

Strength and challenges

Key strengths: Success factors have been to have a network of dedicated researchers in the university and coordinators that act as the link between companies and researchers. Important is also to listen to the companies and put trust in them, and to work with a solid ground based on gender research.

Key challenges: Key challenges are to secure a long term and sustainable financing. The platform has been financed through different types of projects with a lot of funds coming from ERDF/EU financing. Current short-term financing poses a challenge to the long-term sustainability of the project and makes it difficult to scale up - which is an ambition for the future.

Learn more

<https://www.ltu.se/centres/cdt/Gender-Contact-Point>
(This data is taken from LTU Prof. Malin Lindberg paper to G17 Conference)

Summing up and key reflection points

This exercise has asked you to reflect upon promising practices and different ways of addressing the gender gap in technological entrepreneurship. Here we ask you to write down, compare and reflect further on your findings:

Key reflection points:

- What makes this a promising practice?
- What can you take with you as inspiration to your organization?
- What could be improved?
- What new forms of collaborations can you see?

GENRE is a three-year research project that aims to investigate and cross-culturally compare the lived experiences of female technology entrepreneurs in incubation and investing ecosystems in four different countries. The findings generated inform policy development aimed at inclusivity and sustainability, thus benefiting both women and men. It is a transnational research project taking place simultaneously in Ireland (Dublin City University), Norway (Nord University), Sweden (Karlstad and Örebro University) and Israel (Kinneret College). The project is coordinated by DCU Business School (Dublin) and led by Prof Maura McAdam. GENRE is co-funded under the GENDER-NET Plus Joint Call Grant Number GNP-122.

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For updates and project outputs, please visit:
gender-net-plus.eu/genre/

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